

ENA Programmatic Data Submission Practical

As we have discussed, there are three routes of submission:

- Interactive
- Programmatic
- Webin-CLI

In this exercise, you will have the opportunity to submit a set of raw read data to the test version of the **ENA Programmatic Submission** service.

Webin Submissions Portal (TEST): <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

You will need an ENA Webin account to use for this exercise. Webin accounts can be registered on the webin portal 'Register' page:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/accountInfo>

The screenshot shows the 'Webin Submissions Portal' registration page. At the top, there is a header with the ENA logo and the text 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE Webin Submissions Portal'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Account Management'. The main content area is titled 'Account Details' and contains several input fields: 'Abbreviated center name', 'Full center name', 'Laboratory Name', 'Address', and 'Country' on the left; and 'Password' and 'Confirm Password' on the right. Below these fields, there is a section for 'Contact Information' with a button that says 'Add At Least One Contact' and a plus sign icon. At the bottom, there is a checkbox labeled 'No Sensitive Data' with the text 'I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.'

For this practical, you will need the following file formats to complete your submission.

Each section of this practical will show what these files should look like:

1. STUDY: study.json
2. SAMPLE: plant_sample.xml
3. RUN: run_experiment.xml
4. FASTQ: readfile1.fastq.gz
5. FASTQ: readfile2.fastq.gz

It will be helpful to review how the metadata model works. You can find an overview of this here:

[Metadata Model](#)

Throughout this exercise, you are asked to use the ENA test service, which allows you to make submissions which will be removed after 24 hours. If you're not sure if you're in the test server, you can check the address in your browser which will begin 'wwwdev' rather than 'www':

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

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The Scenario

You will be submitting a set of paired read data files derived from truffle oak (*Quercus robur*) tree to the ENA test submission service. This is identical to the production submission service, but submissions are retained for <24 hours. It's therefore perfect for training settings like this.

Some of these exercises require use of the command-line. Where there is a command to run, it will be provided for you mostly complete, indicated by an indented line beginning with a dollar ('\$') sign. Do not enter the \$, just the text following it. Some commands have been left incomplete for you to fill in, so read them carefully before you enter them.

The Study

To begin, you should **register a study**. Recall that a study describes the purpose of the work you have done, groups other objects beneath it, and controls when the data becomes public. A study is required for all submissions to ENA.

1. Prepare a study.json file in JSON format as shown below:

```
{
  "submission": {
    "alias": "",
    "accession": "",
    "actions": [
      {
        "type": "ADD"
      },
      {
        "type": "HOLD",
        "holdUntilDate": "TO DO"
      }
    ]
  },
  "projects": [
    {
      "alias": "TO DO",
      "name": "TO DO",
      "title": "TO DO",
      "description": "TO DO",
      "sequencingProject": {},
      "attributes": [
      ],
      "project_links": [
        {
          "xrefLink": {
            "db": "PUBMED",
            "id": "25035323"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

2. Try and understand the format of the JSON file and look for missing metadata that you will need to populate. This will be labelled as “TO DO”.
3. The SUBMISSION file is merged with the project JSON. What “action” does the submission file indicate?
4. Set a **release date** for your study using HOLD in the submission section of the JSON file (this is when all data associated with the study will be released). This needs to be between now and a maximum of 2 years in the future.
5. The '**name**' field in the study json should be filled in with something brief and meaningful that can help you find and recognise the study.
6. You should take time to provide a descriptive title and informative abstract for your own studies, but these can be edited later if needed. The title could be something similar to:

Evolutionary study of white oak trees from <Your Town/Lab>

7. Are there any publications to link to this study? If so please add them.
8. You now have the three essential components of a programmatic submission:
 - An account name and password
 - An object and its instruction to submit in JSON format
 - An endpoint to send this data to
9. Open a terminal window (CTRL+ALT+T or search) and navigate to the directory containing the files:

```
$ cd file/path
```

10. Type the 'ls' command to view the content of this directory:

```
$ ls -l
```

11. Enter the submission command below, editing it as you go to include the USERNAME, PASSWORD and submission file name (TODO).

```
curl -u username:password -X POST  
'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H  
'Accept: application/json' -H 'Content-Type: application/json'  
-T 'submission file name'
```

Note: If you are using windows terminal you may need to replace the single quotes by double quote

12. Upon successful submission, the terminal will return a success receipt with the project accession.

Make a note of its accession numbers, which will resemble:

ERP##### and PRJEB#####

Note: For a real submission, these would be the numbers you would cite in any publications involving the data.

The Sample

The next step is to register the sample, which will give other users essential context for the sequence data you are submitting. The sample describes the source biological material of your sequencing work.

In ENA, samples are required to conform to a checklist of values. Checklists define a set of mandatory and recommended values for a given type of sample. It is recommended that you look at these early and make sure you collect all required metadata items for the type of sample you will be registering.

The selection of available checklists can be browsed at:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

1. You will now be registering your sample in XML file format. The sample XML should be in a similar format as shown below::
'Plant_sample.xml'

```
<WEBIN>
  <SUBMISSION_SET>
    <SUBMISSION>
      <ACTIONS>
        <ACTION>
          <ADD/>
        </ACTION>
      </ACTIONS>
    </SUBMISSION>
  </SUBMISSION_SET>
  <SAMPLE_SET>
    <SAMPLE alias="TO DO" center_name="">
      <TITLE>TO DO</TITLE>
      <SAMPLE_NAME>
        <TAXON_ID>TO DO</TAXON_ID>
        <SCIENTIFIC_NAME>TO DO</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>
        <COMMON_NAME>TO DO</COMMON_NAME>
      </SAMPLE_NAME>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>
        <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
          <TAG>collection date</TAG>
          <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
        </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
          <TAG>plant growth medium</TAG>
          <VALUE>TO DO: Specification of the media for growing
            the plants or tissue cultured samples. Recommended value is
            a specific value from EO:plant growth medium
            (follow this link for terms http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/EO\_0007147).</VALUE>
        </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
          <TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>
          <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
          <UNITS>DD</UNITS>
        </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        .
        .
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>
    </SAMPLE>
  </SAMPLE_SET>
</WEBIN>
```

Note: Please make sure you use an appropriate checklist for your data type.

Look at the different attributes contained within. Compare these to all the attributes included in the [plant sample checklist here](#). Do you feel this is a well-annotated sample? Go through the sample XML and add any missing metadata fields where you can see “TO DO” in the <VALUE></VALUE> tags.

2. Find the appropriate taxon for your sample: to reiterate what we discussed during the presentation, please use a taxonomy that is as specific as possible. In this case for example, “**Quercus robur**” instead of “**Quercus**”.

- a. This can be looked up on our rest API. Here is an example of a search of “metagenome”:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/metagenome>

You can also search for the species name to find its tax ID on the NCBI Taxonomy database.

- b. NCBI Taxonomy database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

3. Give a 'Unique name' to your sample (sample “alias”)

This value must always be unique among all samples submitted by your account and is a way for you to locate and recognise your specific samples.

4. Give your sample a title, this could look something like:

Truffle oak tree sample from <Your Town/Lab/Location>.

5. Fill out the remaining details.

Tip: You can always find out more about what a field means and what information it accepts by going to the [checklist browser page](#) and reading their description and validation.

Collection date format (year-month-date): 2024-10-24 , 2024-10 , 2024

6. You now have the option of including additional fields in the checklist. It is not necessary to include any additional fields but you can take this opportunity to see which fields are included as mandatory, recommended and optional, what requirements they have, and what else is available [here](#).

7. By the time you have completed this, your sample will be well-annotated and understandable to people finding it in the database later.

8. Next, look at the submission XML included within this file.
What action is specified for this submission?
9. Save the XML file when you have completed the fields and feel the sample is well-annotated.
13. You now have the three essential components of a programmatic submission:
 - An account name and password
 - An object and its instruction to submit in XML format
 - An endpoint to send this data to
14. Open a terminal window (CTRL+ALT+T or search) and navigate to the directory containing the files:

```
$ cd file/path
```

15. Type the 'ls' command to view the content of this directory:

```
$ ls -l
```

16. Enter the submission command below, editing it as you go to include the USERNAME, PASSWORD and submission file name (TODO).

```
curl -u username:password -X POST  
'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H  
'Accept: application/xml' -H 'Content-Type: application/xml'  
-T 'submission file name'
```

Note: If you are using windows terminal you may need to replace the single quotes by double quote

17. Once a submission has been processed a receipt is returned. The **success** attribute in the receipt is **true** if the submission was successful and **false** if the submission was not successful. The receipt also contains the accession numbers of the objects that you have submitted.
18. Find the two sample accessions (SAMEAxxxxx and ERSxxxxxx). Be careful not to confuse the submission accession with these (ERAxxxxxx).

Make a note of its accession numbers as you will need these later:

ERS#####

The Read Data

Now that study and sample metadata have been registered, it is time to upload and submit the read data you have produced.

You will now be submitting a paired set of files:

- readfile1.fastq.gz
- readfile2.fastq.gz

These are the raw read data files you have obtained as a result of sequencing your sample.

Uploading Data Files

Before submitting the read data files, you must upload them. All Webin submission accounts come with a space on our server to upload files to. In most cases, submitters must upload their files to this before they are able to submit.

You will upload files to your private Webin file upload area using either FTP or Aspera protocol through the webin2.ebi.ac.uk service. The authentication is done using your Webin submission account name and password.

1. There are a number of tools and ways to accomplish the upload. For the purpose of this workshop, we will be using FileZilla to upload your read data files. Please install FileZilla client from here: <https://filezilla-project.org/>
2. Open the tool and enter the following details at the top before clicking "Quickconnect":

Host: webin2.ebi.ac.uk
Username: Webin-xxxx
Password: xxxx

3. Once it successfully establishes a connection, you have your local computer paths and files in the windows on the left, and the remote webin upload site on the right. Find the directory with the downloaded paired fastq files and drag the files into the directory listing at the remote site. This will upload your files to your webin upload area.

Webin-47@webin2.ebi.ac.uk - FileZilla

Host: webin2.ebi.ac.uk Username: Webin-47 Password: Port: Quickconnect

Status: Connection established, waiting for welcome message...
Status: Initializing TLS...
Status: TLS connection established.
Status: Logged in
Status: Retrieving directory listing...
Status: Directory listing of "/" successful

Local site: C:\Users\Maira\Desktop\Additional material\testfiles\reads\
Remote site: /

Filename	Filesize	Filetype	Last modified
..			
Assembly		File folder	12/12/2024...
MGrify		File folder	12/12/2024...
reads		File folder	12/12/2024...
file_1.fastq.gz	3,427	GZ File	01/07/2022...
file_1.fastq.gz...	32	MD5 File	07/03/2025...
file_R2.fastq.gz	3,608	GZ File	01/07/2022...
file_R2.fastq.gz...	32	MD5 File	07/03/2025...
manifest.txt	200	Text Docum...	07/08/2024...
manifest.txt.rep...	0	REPORT File	07/08/2024...
manifest1.txt	232	Text Docum...	12/12/2024...

18 files and 1 directory. Total size: 174,551,708 bytes

Empty directory listing

Server/Local file | Dire... | Remote file | Size | Prio... | Status

Queued files | Failed transfers | Successful transfers

Submit Data Files

- You will now be submitting your read files in XML file format. You run and experiment XML should be similar to the format shown below:
'run_experiment.xml'

```

<WEBIN>
  <SUBMISSION_SET>
    <SUBMISSION>
      <ACTIONS>
        <ACTION>
          <ADD/>
        </ACTION>
      </ACTIONS>
    </SUBMISSION>
  </SUBMISSION_SET>
  <EXPERIMENT_SET>
    <EXPERIMENT alias="TO DO">
      <TITLE>TO DO</TITLE>
      <STUDY_REF accession="TO DO"/>
      .
      .
      .
      <PLATFORM>
        <ILLUMINA>
          <INSTRUMENT_MODEL>TO DO</INSTRUMENT_MODEL>
        </ILLUMINA>
      </PLATFORM>
      <EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTES>
        <EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTE>
          <TAG>library preparation date</TAG>
          <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
        </EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTE>
      </EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTES>
    </EXPERIMENT>
  </EXPERIMENT_SET>
  <RUN_SET>
    <RUN alias="TO DO" center_name="">
      <EXPERIMENT_REF refname="TO DO from alias above"/>
      <DATA_BLOCK>
        <FILES>
          <FILE filename="readfile1.fastq.gz" filetype="fastq"
            checksum_method="MD5" checksum="23316bb71b291a61484d6b14d8ae453a"/>
          <FILE filename="readfile2.fastq.gz" filetype="fastq"
            checksum_method="MD5" checksum="40d636c363e1a3a5232d3d1e2feb2c70"/>
        </FILES>
      </DATA_BLOCK>
    </RUN>
  </RUN_SET>
</WEBIN>

```

- Look at the different attributes contained within. Go through the experiment XML and add any missing metadata fields where you can see "TO DO" in the <VALUE></VALUE> tags.

Sample : enter the sample accession here* (ERSxxx)

Study : enter the study accession here* (PRJEBxxx)

Library Name : your lab initials_sequence_library_1

Library Strategy : [Check permitted values](#)

Library Source : [Check permitted values](#)

Library Selection : [Check permitted values](#)

Library Layout : PAIRED

Library Construction Protocol: short description of the protocol

Instrument Model : [Check permitted values](#)

3. Go through the run XML to make sure all the fields have been populated and the type of information that is required for a run submission.

Forward File Name : readfile1.fastq.gz

File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

Reverse File Name : readfile2.fastq.gz

File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

4. Next, look at the submission XML included within this file.
What action is specified for this submission?

5. Save the XML file when you have completed the fields.

19. You now have the three essential components of a programmatic submission:

- An account name and password
- An object and its instruction to submit in XML format
- An endpoint to send this data to

20. Open a terminal window (CTRL+ALT+T or search) and navigate to the directory containing the files:

```
$ cd file/path
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21. Type the 'ls' command to view the content of this directory:

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22. Enter the submission command below, editing it as you go to include the USERNAME, PASSWORD and submission file name (TODO).

```
curl -u username:password -X POST  
'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H  
'Accept: application/xml' -H 'Content-Type: application/xml'  
-T 'submission file name'
```

Note: If you are using windows terminal you may need to replace the single quotes by double quote

23. Once a submission has been processed a receipt is returned. The **success** attribute in the receipt is **true** if the submission was successful and **false** if the submission was not successful. The receipt also contains the accession numbers of the objects

that you have submitted. In this case you will receive a run accession (ERRxxx) and an experiment accession (ERXxxx)